

**Syntheses of Steroidal Dithiolanes and
their Sulphoxides**

SHAFIULLAH*, ISHRAT H. SIDDIQUI

and

SHAHID A. ANSARI

Steroid Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry,
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002

Manuscript received 4 March 1991, accepted 31 May 1991

A number of dithiolanes have been synthesised in recent past¹ owing to their immense pharmacological potentialities². As a sequel to our previous studies, we describes here the syntheses of steroidal dithiolanes and their subsequent oxidation with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid to furnish their respective sulphoxides.

Treatment of 3 β -chloro-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (1)³, its 3 β -hydroxy (2)⁴ and 3 β -acetoxy (3)⁴ analogues with 1,2-ethanedithiol in acetic acid in presence of BF₃-etherate (as a catalyst) furnished the steroidal thioketals (4-6, respectively). These thioketals on oxidation with *m*-chloroperbenzoic

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	δ^{**}
4	130	64	3 400 (OH), 1 435, 1 240 (S-CH ₂), 720 (C-Cl)	4.20 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 16 Hz, axial A/B ring junction <i>trans</i> , C3 α -H), 3.40 (1H, br s, C ₅ -OH) ^a , 3.05 (4H, s, S-CH ₂ CH ₂ -S)
5	Semi-solid	72	3 420 (OH), 1 440, 1 235 (S-CH ₂)	3.85 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 14 Hz, axial, C3 α -H), 3.30 (2H, br s, C3- and C5-OH) ^a , 3.10 (4H, s, S-CH ₂ CH ₂ -S)
6	Oil	71	3 450 (OH), 1 740 (CH ₂ COO), 1 440, 1 240 (S-CH ₂), 1 040 (C-O)	4.72 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 16 Hz, axial, C3 α -H), 3.13 (1H, br s, C ₅ -OH) ^a , 3.05 (4H, s, S-CH ₂ CH ₂ -S), 2.0 (3H, s, CH ₃ COO)
7	Oil	48	3 400 (OH), 1 440, 1 240 (S-CH ₂), 1 060 (S=O), 710 (C-Cl)	4.30 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 14 Hz, axial A/B ring junction <i>trans</i> , C3 α -H), 3.46 (1H, br s, C5-OH) ^a , 3.20 (4H, s, OS-CH ₂ CH ₂ -SO)
8	Oil	56	3 450 (OH), 1 435, 1 235 (S-CH ₂), 1 050 (S=O)	3.95 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 15 Hz, axial, C3 α -H), 3.25 (4H, s, OS-CH ₂ CH ₂ -SO), 2.75 (2H, br s, C3- and C5-OH) ^a
9	Semi-solid	54	3 430 (OH), 1 745 (CH ₂ COO), 1 440, 1 240 (S-CH ₂), 1 050 (S=O)	4.80 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 15 Hz, axial, C3 α -H), 3.20 (4H, s, OS-CH ₂ CH ₂ -SO), 3.00 (1H, br s, C5-OH) ^a , 2.05 (3H, s, CH ₃ COO)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses ; Solvent of elution : petroleum ether-ether ratio 30 : 1 4 ; 10 : 1 5 ; 20 : 1 6 ; 14 : 1 7 ; 5 : 1 8 ; 10 : 1 9.

**Angular and side chain methyl protons appeared at δ 1.25–0.66 ; ^aExchangeable with deuterium.

acid provided steroidal sulphoxides (7–9, respectively). The structures of the compounds were supported by their elemental analyses and nmr⁵ and ir⁶ spectral data.

1, 4, 7 ; R=Cl
2, 5, 8 ; R=OH
3, 6, 9 ; R=OAc

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were obtained on a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A-60D instrument using TMS as internal standard.

Reaction of 5 α -hydroxy ketones (1–3) with 1,2-ethanedithiol-BF₃-etherate. *General procedure:* A solution of the ketone (1; 1.0 g, 2.28 mmol) in acetic acid (30 ml) was treated with 1,2-ethanedithiol (0.5 ml) and freshly distilled BF₃-etherate (1.0 ml) and left at room temperature for 48 h. The progress of reaction was monitored by tlc. The solution was then diluted with methanol (5.0 ml), poured into water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent gave an oily residue which was chromatographed over silica gel (20 g) to obtain dithiolanes (4–6; Table 1).

Oxidation of steroidal dithiolanes (4–6) with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid. *General procedure:* To a stirred solution of the dithiolane (4; 0.5 g, 0.97 mmol) in dichloromethane (40 ml) was added *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (0.340 g, 1.95 mmol) in portions at room temperature and stirred for 36 h. It was then diluted with dichloromethane (20 ml) and was washed with water, sodium bisulphite solution (10%) to destroy unreacted peracid and then with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent gave an oily residue which on column chromatography over silica gel (10 g) afforded steroidal sulphoxides (7–9; Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. M. A. Beg, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, for facilities. Financial assistances from I.C.M.R. to one of the authors (I.H.S.) and from U.G.C., New Delhi, to the other (S.A.A.) are gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. J. W. RALLS, R. M. DODSON and B. RIEGEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3320; L. F. FIESER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1945; S. M. KUPCHAN, S. MCLEAN, G. W. A. MILNE and P. SLADE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 147; M. NUMAZAWA, M. TSUJI and R. OSADA, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1986, **54**.
2. D. R. CRUMP, *J. Chem. Ecol.*, 1980, **6**, 837; K. TANINAKA *Rev. Plant Prot. Res.*, 1979, **12**, 24; T. WIELAND, A. DEBOEN and H. FAULSTICH, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1980, 416.
3. C. W. SHOPPÉE, R. J. BRIDGEWATER, D. N. JONES and G. H. R. SUMMERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2492.
4. L. F. FIESER and S. RAJAGOPALAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3938.

5. N. S. BHACCA and D. H. WILLIAMS, "Applications of NMR Spectroscopy in Organic Chemistry", Holden Day, San Francisco, 1964.
6. L. J. BELLAMY, "The ir Spectra of Complex Molecules", Wiley, New York, 1958.